

A Simply Updatable Cloud-based Ensemble Digital Terrain Model

Yu-Feng Ho
OpenGeoHub
Wageningen, Netherlands
yu-feng.ho@opengeohub.org

Tomislav Hengl
OpenGeoHub
Wageningen, Netherlands
tom.hengl@opengeohub.org

Leandro Parente
OpenGeoHub
Wageningen, Netherlands
leandro.parente@opengeohub.org

Abstract—A wide range of global public topography datasets circulates to service for various purposes. However, the variety of versions, sources, and formats can confuse users and lead to decrease of usage. Users typically require a single terrain model that can be used to produce morphometric and hydrographic terrain variables across borders. An Ensemble Digital Terrain Model (EDTM) by deriving from global public elevation maps and national DTMs, serves as a simply updatable and inclusive map. To further increase the usability, the concept of Analysis-Ready Cloud Optimized (ACRO) on the basis of cloud optimized GeoTIFF (COG) is adopted. ACRO optimizes accessibility by its pyramid structure of overviews and provides data preprocessing and reformatting in an open source, well-documented and reproducible workflow. EDTM aims to reduce the complexity of global elevation datasets and make the data more usable.

optimized GeoTIFF (COG) targets web-optimized access to raster data, having a pyramid structure of overviews based on tiles. This characteristic allows clients to retrieve the data by allocating to the suitable overview and loading sufficient tiles for visualization[4]. Upon COG, Analysis-Ready Cloud Optimized (ACRO) is the next generation of big earth data, providing data with preprocessing and reformatting, in order to lift the burden of environmental scientists. Furthermore, an open source, well-documented and reproducible workflow is required, so as users evaluate the suitability for their particular analytic task[5].

To help reduce the complexity of global elevation datasets and make the data more usable. We collect global public topography datasets (GLO-30, ALOS AW3D, and MERIT DEM) and nation DTMs (NDTMs), and create a multipurpose Ensemble DTM (EDTM) for the world. Furthermore, the ensemble map is simply updatable, inclusive, and in ACRO.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years a number of global public topography datasets at high spatial resolutions (30 m) have been released including GLO-30 and ALOS AW3D, and that is on top of the existing NASADEM, ASTER DEM, MERIT DEM and similar.

Land-use planners, hydrologists, geomorphologists and a wide range of public and private sectors rely on a digital elevation map in their workflow. However, too many versions, sources, and formats can often confuse users and decrease the usability of each data. In addition, most DEMs produced from remote sensing observations are only surface models requiring removal of canopy and similar objects. Users typically require a single (most current, most accurate, most complete) terrain model that can then be used to produce morphometric and hydrographic terrain variables across borders[1][2].

Accessibility, huge data volume, non-standardized format, too many portals and platforms, and data discovery are five biggest challenges when it comes to open big earth data[3]. Cloud

II. ENSEMBLE TERRAIN MODEL IN 30M (EDTM30)

A. Concept

Although terrain can be estimated using ICESat / GEDI points as reference training data, we adopt a more simple procedure for building a DTM that allows for faster updates and easy additions of new data: using lower 10% probability quantile. Advantage of having an inexpensive setup to update Ensemble DTM (EDTM30) is that we could possibly run nightly updates, as soon as countries or regions submit locally produced terrain models.

Considering that terrain heights are at the lower part of the distribution, we simply derive a 10% lower quantile from multi source data (Figure 1). We assume that, because canopy is difficult to remove and still remains even in MERIT DEM and FABDEM[6], deriving 10% lower quantile can further help filter

out potential canopy remains. The global public datasets and NDTMs are listed in Table I.

B. Methodology

To be computational efficiency, the process is run as the flow chart above, with tile by tile (1,000 x 1,000 pixels). In summary the process works as follows: firstly standard deviation (s.d.) is derived using the list of DEMs (new map). For GLO-30, ALOS, all pixels where s.d. values are greater than 6 m (60 dm) and/or where canopy height is greater than 2m are removed[7]. Subsequently, a lower 10% quantile is derived from GLO-30, ALOS AW3D, MERIT DEM, and NDTMs. Finally, the standard deviation among all maps is derived and used as the uncertainty map.

The process of deriving the estimate is fully documented and automated in Python script (https://github.com/openlandmap/spatial-layers/blob/main/EDTM/ensemble_dtm.ipynb). The generation of an EDTM takes 5 hours running on a fully parallelized high performance computing center (HPC) with Common Component Architecture (CCA) 1050 threads under the framework of Slurm. However, final mosaic of the world is a massive ~200GB dataset and takes about 3 days to compile a COG using GDAL (<https://gdal.org>).

C. Result

Two output layers are produced as ARCO GeoTIFF, which are (1) EDTM in meter, and (2) standard deviation, showing biggest discrepancies between ALOS AW3D, GLO-30, MERIT DEM, and national DTMs.

To access this dataset seamlessly, the global mosaic to COG files are uploaded to S3 repository. Data are hosted accordingly: (1) EDTM in meter, (https://s3.eu-central-1.wasabisys.com/openlandmap/dtm/dtm.bareearth_ensemble_p10_30m_s_2018_go_epsg4326_v20230221.tif), and (2) standard deviation (https://s3.eu-central-1.wasabisys.com/openlandmap/dtm/dtm.bareearth_ensemble_std_30m_s_2018_go_epsg4326_v20230221.tif).

A demonstration of the maps used and the results obtained (EDTM) is shown in Figure 2. Masked out areas are mainly hills and mountains, and the uncertainty in these areas is also higher. It indicates that the difference in elevation at mountainous regions is significant among DEMs. Figure 3 illustrates the overview of global EDTM.

D. Figures and Tables

Figure 1. Workflow of Ensemble Digital Terrain Model

Figure 2. Input maps and EDTM, and the standard deviation (uncertainty) map around Iași

Figure 3. Global EDTM in an overview

TABLE I. LIST OF PUBLIC GLOBAL, REGIONAL, AND NATIONAL MAPS USED FOR MODELING EDTM

Name of map	Information		
	Type	Type	DOI
GLO-30	Digital surface model (DSM)	Globe (without Azerbaijan)	https://doi.org/10.5270/ESA-c5d3d65

Name of map	Information		
	Type	Type	DOI
ALOS AW3D	Digital surface model (DSM)	Globe	https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsannals-II-4-71-2014
MERIT DEM	Digital terrain model (DTM)	Globe	https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL072874
Dtm_eumap (EcoDataCube)	Digital terrain model (DTM)	Europe	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724549
Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of Australia, Lidar	Digital terrain model (DTM)	Coastal and Urban area in Australia	https://doi.org/10.26186/789644
Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of USA, Lidar	Digital terrain model (DTM)	United States	https://doi.org/10.3133/fs20193032

- Dandabathula, G., Hari, R., Ghosh, K., Bera, A. K., & Srivastav, S. K., 2022. Accuracy assessment of digital bare-earth model using ICESat-2 photons: analysis of the FABDEM. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-022-01648-4>
- Potapov, P., Li, X., Hernandez-Serna, A., Tyukavina, A., Hansen, M. C., Kommareddy, A., ... & Hofton, M., 2021. Mapping global forest canopy height through integration of GEDI and Landsat data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 253, 112165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.112165>

III. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been funded by OEMC project The Open-Earth-Monitor Cyberinfrastructure project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement [No 101059548](https://doi.org/10.101059548).

REFERENCES

- Amatulli, G., Domisch, S., Tuanmu, M. N., Parmentier, B., Ranipeta, A., Malczyk, J., & Jetz, W., 2018. A suite of global, cross-scale topographic variables for environmental and biodiversity modeling. *Scientific data*, 5(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.40>
- Amatulli, G., Garcia Marquez, J., Sethi, T., Kiesel, J., Grigoropoulou, A., Üblacker, M. M., ... & Domisch, S., 2022. Hydrography90m: A new high-resolution global hydrographic dataset. *Earth System Science Data*, 14(10), 4525-4550. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-14-4525-2022>
- Wagemann, J., Siemen, S., Seeger, B., & Bendix, J., 2021. Users of open Big Earth data—An analysis of the current state. *Computers & Geosciences*, 157, 104916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2021.104916>
- Iosifescu Enescu, I., de Espona, L., Haas-Artho, D., Kurup Buchholz, R., Hanimann, D., Rüetschi, M., ... & Pellissier, L., 2021. Cloud optimized raster encoding (core): A web-native streamable format for large environmental time series. *Geomatics*, 1(3), 369-382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geomatics1030021>
- Stern, C., Abernathey, R., Hamman, J., Wegener, R., Lepore, C., Harkins, S., & Merose, A., 2022. Pangeo Forge: Crowdsourcing Analysis-Ready, Cloud Optimized Data Production. *Frontiers in Climate*, 3, 179. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.782909>